

Synthesis and Evaluation of Anti-Cancer Activity on Human Breast Cancer Cell Line MFC7 of Some Novel Thiazolidino (3,2-b)-1, 2,4-Triazole-5(6H)-one Derivatives

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Abstract : Novel thiazolidino-(3,2-b)-1, 2,4-triazole-5(6H)-one derivatives were synthesized, and anticancer activity was studied on human breast cancer cell line MFC7. It showed a significant decrease in cell viability with reference to the standard. The findings suggest that nitro-substituted compound showed best anticancer activity and activity was due to the triazole and thiazolidinone hetero nucleus present in the structure.

Keywords : anti-cancer, adriamycine, thiazolidinone, 1, 2,4-triazole, thiazolidino-triazolone

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